

MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6567962>

Teshayeva Maftuna

Uzakova Malika

*Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health
named after Abu Ali ibn Sino*

Abstract: *Myocardial infarction is an acute condition, a clinical form of ischemic heart disease, caused by necrosis (death) of heart muscle tissue (myocardium) as a result of complete or partial anemia. This leads to disruption of the entire cardiovascular system and endangers the patient's life.*

The main and most common cause of myocardial infarction is a disruption of blood flow in the coronary arteries, which supply the heart muscle with blood and, accordingly, oxygen. Most often, this disorder occurs against the background of atherosclerosis of the arteries, in which atherosclerotic plaques form on the walls of blood vessels. These plaques narrow the cavity of the coronary arteries and contribute to damage to the vessel walls, which creates additional conditions for the formation of thrombi and arterial stenosis.

This acute condition has its own set of symptoms, and they are usually so obvious that they may not go unnoticed. However, it should be borne in mind that there are also atypical forms of this disease.

In most cases, patients develop a usually painful form of myocardial infarction, as a result of which the doctor is able to accurately diagnose the disease and begin treatment immediately.

The main symptom of the disease is severe pain. The pain associated with a myocardial infarction is located behind the chest, which feels like a burning sensation and a stab wound, and some patients describe the pain as “tearing”. The pain can spread to the left arm, lower jaw, and between the shoulders. The development of this condition does not always come after physical exertion, and most often the pain syndrome occurs at rest or in the evening. Although the described features of the pain symptom are similar to those seen in angina attacks, there are clear differences that distinguish them from each other.

Unlike an angina attack, the pain syndrome caused by a myocardial infarction lasts more than 30 minutes and does not stop with a state of calm or repeated administration of nitroglycerin. It should be noted that if the painful attack lasts more than 15 minutes, and the measures taken are ineffective, an emergency medical team should be called immediately.

TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIC INFARCTION

The patient may be suspected of having a myocardial infarction if:

Pain accompanied by a strong burning sensation in the back of the chest, lasting more than 5-10 minutes;

The pain does not go away over time, after calming down or taking nitroglycerin;

The pain is accompanied by severe weakness, nausea, vomiting, headache and dizziness.

If you suspect a myocardial infarction, call an ambulance immediately and start helping the patient. The earlier the patient receives first aid, the more positive the outcome.

The load on the heart should be reduced, so the patient should lie down with his head slightly raised. Efforts should be made to provide fresh air and sedation, and sedatives may be given.

The patient should place a nitroglycerin tablet (pre-crushed) under the tongue and chew one aspirin tablet.

If there are drugs in the beta-blocker group (Atenolol, Metoprolol), the patient should be given 1 tablet for chewing (exactly for chewing, otherwise it does not work). If the patient is taking these medications regularly, he or she should be able to tolerate an extra dose of the medication.

To reduce the pain, the patient should be given analgesics (analgin, baralgin, etc.).

In addition, the patient can take one tablet of panangin or 60 drops of corvalol.

If cardiac arrest is suspected (fainting, respiratory arrest, lack of pulse and failure to respond to external stimuli), resuscitation measures (artificial respiration and indirect cardiac massage) should be initiated immediately. If the patient does not regain consciousness, the treatment should be continued until the doctors arrive.

REFERENCES:

1. M.F.Ziyayeva. Z.O.Rizayeva. “Bolalarda hamshiralik parvarishi”. Toshkent, “Fan va texnologiya” 2012 yil.
2. X.N Fayziyev. « Сестринский уход за детьми » Toshkent, «Илм ziyoy» nashriyoti, 2008 yil
3. K.S Inomov. «Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi» Toshkent, 2007 yil
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. <https://mymedic.uz/>